

Living Lab and International Cooperation in Tertiary Education

Authors

Sangsup Ha¹, Sujung Nam¹, Jeong-In Lee¹, Sangbum Shin¹

¹Institute for Poverty Alleviation & International Development (IPAID), Yonsei University, South Korea

Abstract

Living labs are a series of problem-solving and innovation activities carried out by citizens, scientists, specialists, governments, and firms. If used in college education, living labs become a typical example of a community-based problem-solving learning method. In this study, a project on international educational cooperation based on living lab activities will be introduced. Three universities from three different countries have been invited by our host university, and these four universities are implementing living lab projects simultaneously. The results will be shared once the project is completed, and the similarities and differences in the project outcomes will be analysed. To date, two cooperative models have been identified. First, students in different countries can focus on similar problems but come up with different solutions based on their political, economic, social, and cultural conditions. Second, students in different countries can focus on different problems but can cooperate to address the problem more effectively.

Keywords

living lab, problem-solving, tertiary education, international educational cooperation

Introduction

Living labs are a series of activities, such as generating ideas, designing, and implementing experiments, and developing innovative technologies, carried out by citizens in cooperation with researchers, government officials, firms, and other specialists to address local problems in their communities. If used in college education, living labs become a typical example of a community-based problem-solving learning method. Students are organised as groups, attempting to find problems in the college town (or on campus), design and implement experiments, produce a prototype, and apply it to designated problems. Professors can use living labs as a learning tool in college education, with the expectation that living lab activities can promote students' creativity and empower their problem-solving skills and abilities.¹

We major in social science disciplines such as political science, international relations, public policy, and education. We taught several undergraduate classes in which students experienced parts of a living lab project, such as International Development Cooperation and Global Environmental Politics. In these classes, students identify local problems, come up with ideas for solutions, and design living lab experiments based on their solutions. After the semester, if students want to conduct the experiment they have designed, they apply for government-organised living lab contests. If accepted, a budget and other support are provided to carry out the experiment. They produce prototypes, apply them to local problems, and in some cases, they invent business models based on the results.

Based on these experiences of living lab-based educational innovation, we recently launched a new research project titled 'Living Lab and International Cooperation in Tertiary Education'. The basic idea is that multiple universities in diverse countries simultaneously organise and implement living lab activities in their undergraduate classes, and participating students and professors share their processes and results. The goals of these cooperative projects are (1) to help students understand the 'glocal' way of problem-solving (how global problems are defined and addressed differently in different local areas); (2) to guide students in finding possible political, economic, social, and

¹ Ann-Louise Davidson, Ariel Harlap and Nadia Bhuiyan, "A Living Lab Approach to Prepare Students to Be Confident Innovators," *Revue Interventions Economiques*, 68(2022); See following articles on PBL in general. Jonathan Williamson & Alison S. Gregory, "Problem-Based Learning in Introductory American Politics Classes," *Journal of Political Science Education*, 6:3(July 2010); Heidi M. Berggren, "Problem-Based Learning and Improved Learning Outcomes in "The Politics of Welfare Reform"," *Journal of Political Science Education*, 7:4(October 2011).

cultural conditions that might generate different processes and outcomes of the living lab class activities across the countries; and (3) to help students thrive as global citizens and cultivate the sense of global responsibility. In addition, as researchers, we will explore how these activities impact students' academic competence, creativity, and problem-solving abilities and how and why this impact varies across countries and/or regions.

This project is unique in terms that it focuses on multiple cases in different countries while existing living lab projects deal with one problem in a certain place. Comparing and contrasting each case in diverse countries would lead to a new way of problem solving. We expect that the project would extend the boundaries of living lab and can be a new model for international cooperation at the university level.²

In this paper, we first introduce the project outline and its background motivations. We then present what we have done to date and what we expect from it. Finally, we discuss two important findings that have been reported to date.

Project Outline

The project was initiated in September 2022 when our research institute received a government research fund designed for international educational cooperation. The estimated duration of the project is six years. Our research institute is an institute stipulated in the international development cooperation. It organises and implements official developmental assistance (ODA). The original plan for this research project was to cooperate with local universities located at ODA project sites. This would not only save time and energy in finding partner universities, but we could also expect some synergistic effect on existing ODA partnerships between the two sides. However, we identified other general partners and extended our partnership to other universities.

The 6-year period is divided into two parts. **Part I** is divided into three stages. In **the first stage**, participating universities implement living lab classes separately with baseline (minimum) coordination (such as schedules and forms of activities). In **the second stage**, we designate similar courses in the same academic disciplines and implement living lab activities. For example, the participating universities are all political science majors, and they open courses on environmental politics. The living lab activities are implemented in the same context as the course objectives. In **the third stage**, a common course titled

² Katharina Greve, Riccardo De Vita, Seppo Leminen and Mika Westerlund, "Living Labs: From Niche to Mainstream Innovation Management," *Sustainability*, 13:2(January 2021).

‘Living Lab and Social Innovation’ is available to all participating universities with the same course outline and syllabus. The course objectives, student responsibilities, curriculum, living lab activities, and evaluations are all fully coordinated. In **Part II**, while maintaining the basic framework for cooperation, we include more participants from various academic disciplines beyond the social sciences. We also extend our cooperative project to graduate-level seminars. Additionally, we may be able to develop a new model for educational ODA projects based on these living lab activities. In the future, we shall implement our educational ODA model at partner universities.

Progress to date

We first developed a manual and teaching portfolio for living lab class cooperation. In the manual, we introduced specific directions and stages of living lab activities. The teaching portfolio included a syllabus, handouts, examples of previous presentations, and other teaching materials. We distributed these to our partner universities and held a series of online and offline workshops to share opinions and decide on a cooperative framework for the first year.

The framework has been planned and implemented as a five-step process:

Step 1. At the beginning of the semester, the instructor introduces the entire project to students, especially focusing on the meaning of the project in the context of the course.

Step 2. The instructor explains the meaning of a living lab and its importance to the context of the course and gives examples of living lab projects for students. In some cases, we provide special lectures to partner university students to introduce a living lab.

Step 3. Students are grouped, and their living lab activities are initiated. They are supposed to identify problems, gather (or create) data, determine their cause(s), and develop solutions. All groups present their projects in their classrooms (Table 1).

Step 4. Students upload a short video clip explaining the group project outline to the YouTube channel. In this way, students in different universities share projects. They write a short response memo for their partner university’s projects and send them to partner universities. Once they have received a memo, they read it and discuss it themselves.

Step 5. All the participating professors meet at a conference in late August in the host country to share their projects and discuss possible research cooperation for publication. In addition, they discuss the future directions for further cooperation in the next semester.

Table 1. Examples of Presentations

Problems	Causes	Solutions
Lack of educational opportunities for female students	Early marriage traditions in the ethnic minorities	Education to increase awareness
Blind people cannot recognise the colour of apparel and shoes when they shop for them or keep them at home.	Visual handicap, but at the same time, social exclusion of disabled people	Make rubber tags indicating the colour in Braille and attach them to the clothes and shoes Suggest apparel companies include this tag in their product as a campaign
Slow business of local shop owners	COVID-19, but also shop owners are older individuals not familiar with e-commerce	Students cooperate with shop owners to develop applications for online shopping
Patients visiting hospitals have a hard time with taking their medical procedures.	Hospitals have congested facilities and complicated system process.	Make a wearable hospital device to let patients know complicated medical procedures.

For research purposes, we conducted a pre-project survey of students in five classes. After completing the project, we will conduct a post-project survey with the same students. A questionnaire was designed to examine the possible effects of the living lab project on students' problem-solving abilities and creativity. We also plan to conduct semi-structured interviews with students during and after the project. Eventually, we will write papers titled, 'The impact of living lab classes on students' problem-solving ability and creativity', 'Local-to-local educational cooperation and its implications on existing international development cooperation', 'Socioeconomic conditions affecting the differences in the process and outcomes of living lab class activities in different countries'.

Findings

There are at least two findings to share at this moment.

First, we identify at least two patterns that could potentially become models of cooperation. First, students at different universities (in different countries) encounter similar problems, but the solutions are different. We found that one group in Vietnam and another in Indonesia designated early marriage as the same problem. However, they focused on different aspects of the problem, and their solutions were different. Therefore, we can compare and contrast them and analyse possible factors contributing to these differences. Second, students in different universities (in different countries) face different problems, but there is the possibility of generating cooperative solutions. For example, students in Indonesia and the host country could cooperate to establish an online

marketing mechanism that targets the Korean market. This will help boost the local economy on the Indonesian side but simultaneously help the host country’s students overcome their limited job opportunities.

Second, we have been concerned about the limited opportunities for the actual implementation of living lab activities when the semester is over in partner universities. In the case of the host country, there are a number of opportunities to apply for the actual implementation of the experiment. As mentioned previously, there are many government-driven laboratory tests in Korea. Our concern is that partner universities may have some problems finding additional funding sources for actual experiments. However, this was not a factor that delayed cooperation. Since professors at partner universities have realised the importance of living lab projects, they have become enthusiastic about finding funding sources for their students. In addition, we will attempt to find ways to conduct cooperative experiments between the host and partner universities. We hope that this project will create new possibilities for international cooperation of the living lab in the future. In addition, in terms of education, we hope to find new implications (both theoretical and policy) in our project and research and contribute to existing discussions on the effectiveness of various teaching and learning methods.³

³Carina Veeckman, Dimitra Schuurman, Seppo Leminen and Mika Westerlund, “Linking Living Lab Characteristics and Their Outcomes: Towards a Conceptual Framework,” *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 3:12(December 2013).

References

1. Berggren, Heidi M.(2011). "Problem-Based Learning and Improved Learning Outcomes in "The Politics of Welfare Reform"." *Journal of Political Science Education*, 7:4.
2. Davidson, Ann-Louise, Harlap, Ariel, and Bhuiyan, Nadia (2022). "A Living Lab Approach to Prepare Students to Be Confident Innovators." *Revue Interventions Economiques*, 68.
3. Greve, Katharina, De Vita, Riccardo, Leminen, Seppo, and Westerlund, Mika (2021). "Living Labs: From Niche to Mainstream Innovation Management." *Sustainability*, 13:2.
4. Veeckman, Carina, Schuurman, Dimitra, Leminen, Seppo, and Westerlund, Mika (2013). "Linking Living Lab Characteristics and Their Outcomes: Towards a Conceptual Framework." *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 3:12.
5. Williamson, Jonathan and Gregory, Alison S.(2010). "Problem-Based Learning in Introductory American Politics Classes." *Journal of Political Science Education*, 6:3.

